

Plant Extracts Mediated Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles and their Catalytical, Biological and Carcinogenic Applications: A review

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Abstract: Since the 1980s, nanotechnology has experienced a revival and it has commercial, industrial, agricultural, and therapeutic uses. Ancient dynasties and nations used silver vastly. Silver nanostructures have better antibacterial activity, electrical and thermal conductivities, optical and mechanical properties over bulk silver. Due to the difficulties of physical and chemical methods, simplified techniques and materials are being developed. This review explains how green chemistry can improve processes and replace physical and chemical synthesis. Recently, plant-mediated synthesis has gained attention due to its simple culturing processes and scalability. This review talks about the wide variety of plants that can be used to make fast, one-step protocols for figuring out what nanoparticles are made of. It also talks about different biological activities, such as anti-fungal, anti-cancer, and anti-bacterial activities.

Key words: Bio diversity, Green synthesis, Silver nanoparticles, Antimicrobial activity

1. INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology has been around since the 1980s and has witnessed a renaissance in the early 2000s. Nano particles have commercial, industrial, agricultural, and therapeutic uses. Nanoparticles may have different colour, strength, magnetic and thermodynamic properties than the parent material [1]. Nano particles biological, physical, and chemical properties are the key factors for their vast use in biomedicine, food and environment, optics, chemical industries, electronics, space industries, and science [2].

Silver nanostructures have many promising applications in the field of nanoscience. Ancient dynasties and nations used silver extensively. Caldeans used silver for food storage in 4000 B.C. [3] and Persians, Romans, Egyptians, and Greeks are also did the same thing [4]. Since ancient times, silver (Ag) has been used in medicine to treat a wide variety of ailments because of its wide spectrum of antibacterial and therapeutic qualities [5-6].

Silver NPs have gained attention in recent times due to their enhanced antimicrobial efficacy, electrical, thermal conductivities, optical and mechanical properties compared to bulk silver. Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) have biomedical and therapeutic applications. [7-9]. AgNPs were used to produce thermally conductive materials and to improve conductivity in polymer composites [10, 11]. AgNPs have also shown distinct electrical characteristics. The electrical conductivity of polycarbonate composites has been improved by coating polycarbonate substrates with AgNPs [12].

In general, two methods, known as the 'top-down method' and 'bottom-up method', are employed in the synthesis of NPs. These two approaches can fall into three different categories like physical, chemical, and biological routes. [13].

Some of the physical methods used in the synthesis of Nps are crushing, grinding, evaporation, condensation. But toxic chemicals are used in chemical synthesis. In the biological methods, NPs are synthesized by means of plants [14-17], bacterial [18-21], yeast or fungi [22-28]. The biological methods of synthesizing NPs are come under green synthesis due to its environment friendly. Presently green methods of synthesizing NPs are preferred over other methods due to lack of hazardous chemical involvement, less cost, low toxic nature, results in high yield and feasibility for large scale synthesis [29-31].

Due to the drawbacks of physical and chemical procedures, attention has been focused on the development of simple techniques and materials that are less harmful and more economical. The choice of naturally occurring procedures, also referred to as "green processes," has been a popular topic in this area. However, the term "green synthesis" of silver NPs refers to the manufacture of silver nanostructures utilising eco-friendly methods. Thus, only biological methods are used to synthesise these materials. For instance, alternative reagents like ascorbic acid and sodium citrate are thought to be able to synthesis AgNPs in an eco-friendly way [32]. The top-down synthesis of silver nanostructures using high-energy consuming processes has been largely disregarded for the green synthesis of silver nanostructures [33-35]. Although there have been significant advancements in the green synthesis of silver NPs over the past ten years, there are still problems with stability, size distribution, morphology, and unidentified biological functions as well as the fact that some biological processes cannot be applied in an industrial processes because of stringent and time-consuming process. [36,37].

Fig. 1: Various methods for synthesis of nanoparticles

In this review, we discuss the advantages of green chemistry act as an alternative method compared to other methods. Among the green synthesis procedures, significant attention has been given to plant-mediated synthesis due to its simple culturing procedures. Therefore it is required to search for greener reagents for the preparation of nanoparticles [38]. We show how plant-mediated synthesis can emerge as a novel and alternative methodology towards the preparations of AgNPs, which have diverse applications in various fields.

2. PLANT MEDIATED SYNTHESIS OF NANOPARTICLES

Plant extracts are one of the best sources for the synthesis of nanoparticles because they are not having any harmful chemicals and also they acts as reducing and capping agents for nanoparticles that keep them stable. Plant-mediated synthesis of metal NPs is becoming more popular because it is easy to use, fast, can make different shapes, and is good for the environment. Biosynthesis uses plants because they have important reducing agents like alkaloids, amino acids, proteins/enzymes, polysaccharides, polyphenols and vitamins citric acid, ascorbic acid, flavonoids etc. They are very important for making nanoparticles through biosynthesis. [39]

Many studies have been prepared by green synthesis of Ag NPs using a variety of Plant parts such as leaves, flowers, stems, roots, bark, seed, peels etc. In plant mediated synthesis of Ag NPs, extractions are made from plant materials are added to an aqueous AgNO_3 solution, In the process, Ag ions in the aqueous solution undergo the reduction process to form Ag NPs. Silver ions act as electron acceptors and the bio molecules present in the plant extracts act as reducing agents which are responsible for reduction of the silver ion. [13, 40]

In plant mediated synthesis, various factors such as the “volume” of plant extract, the volume of plant extract and AgNO₃ solution ratio. The concentration of the metal ion, reaction time, reaction temperature, and the reaction pH can affect the Ag NPs formation. In the process of synthesis, plant materials were washed and they are shade dried in the open air. The dried plant parts were powdered and extracted with a solvent by heating. These plant extract is mixed with milli molar concentrations of AgNO₃ in subsequent ratios. Temperature, heat (or) sun light catalyses the reaction. Completion of the reaction is indicated by the colour change (pale yellow to red-orange) [41, 42 and 43].

Literature review revealed that, up on increase of metal ion concentration, particle sizes also increases. The longer reaction time sharpens the UV-Visible spectra, indicating an increment of the concentration of NPs. However after some time agglomeration takes place in resulting bigger particles. The rise in temperature has increased the rate of formation of the NPs whereas the acidic environment suppress, while the basic conditions support Ag NPs formation [44, 45–49]

The powder form of Ag NPs from the solution is obtained by Centrifugation. Trials at various rounds per minute values (5000–10,000 rpm) and various time periods (from 10 minutes to over 20 minutes) are conducted in order to optimise the rounds per minute and time durations for centrifuging samples. [47, 50, 51, 52]. Ag NP suspensions are dried to produce the final product in powder form. [53]

3. PROPERTIES OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES

The chemical, mechanical, optical, electrical, and magnetic properties of nanomaterials change significantly due to surface effects and quantum effects. As a result, nano silver has distinct optical and physical properties that are not found in bulk silver and are extremely useful in medical applications. Silver nanoparticles are primarily used in antibacterial, antifungal [54], antiviral [55], anti-inflammatory, and other applications.[56]

Since ancient times, people have known that silver can be used for various medical purposes. AgNPs were used as antimicrobial agents from long time, are also used in textiles, food additives, packaging, and plastics. Because silver has so many uses, many ways have been found to make silver nanoparticles and silver-based compounds that contain metallic silver [57]. Antimicrobial Nano paint made with silver nanoparticles is good for the environment [58], and the antimicrobial properties of silver ions are important in food packaging systems [59]. Silver ions that are formed in the reaction give silver nanoparticles show antibacterial properties [60], and they are used as preservatives in food and other industries .People say that silver nanoparticles help wounds heal and make people look better. [61]. Nowadays nanostructured compounds have become facile adsorbent materials for the efficient removal of water pollutants [62].

Table 1: Summary of silver nano particles synthesized via a green approach.

S.no	Plants used	Plants parts used	Size of NPs(nm)	Shape of nano particles	Ref.
Leaves extract					
1	Ziziphora tenuior	Leaf	8-40	Spherical	63
2	Calotropis procera	Leaf	8-20	Spherical	64
3	Psoralea corylifolia	Leaf	50-100	Square ,rod	65
4	Aloe vera	Leaf	15.2+-4.2	Spherical	66
5	Datura metal	Leaf	40-60	Irregular	67
6	Ficus bengalinsis	Leaf	10-50	Spherical	68
7	Moringa olifera	Leaf	57	Spherical	69
8	Kalanchoe pinnata	Leaf	84.85	Crystalline	70
9	Lantana camara	Leaf	20nm	Spherical	71
10	E oleosa	Leaves	21	Spherical	72
11	Ziziphus jujuba	Leaf	20-30	Irregular	73
12	Prosopis farcta	Leaf	10.8	Spherical	74
13	Indoneesiella echioides	Leaf	29	Spherical	75
14	Dolichos lablab.L	Leaf	9	Spherical	76
15	Viola serpens	Leaves	85	Spherical	77
16	Grewia flaviscences	Leaves	60	Spherical	78
17	Clerodendrum serratum	Leaves	18	Spherical	79
18	Averrhoa carambola	Leaves	14	Spherical	80
19	Rosmarinus officinalis	Leaves	22	Spherical	81

20	Carica papaya	Leaves	80	Spherical	82
21	Plukenetia volubilis	Leaves	15	Optical	83
22	Annona muricata	Leaves	27	Spherical	84
23	Justicia adhatoda	Leaves	25	Spherical	85
24	Hemidesmus indicus	Leaves	25.24	Spherical	86
25	Ficus hispida Linn. F	Leaves	30.5	Spherical	87
26	Saraca indica	Leaf	23	Spherical	88
27	Viburnum lantana	Leaves	2-80	Spherical	89
28	Garcinia mangostana	Leaves	35	Spherical	90
29	Datura stramonium	Leaves	15-20	Spherical	91
Other parts of the plant extracts					
30	Ficus carica	Fruit	54-89	Spherical	92
31	Garcinia mangostana	Stem	15-20	Spherical	93
32	Pistacia atlantica	Seeds	10-50	Spherical	94
33	Tephrosia tinctoria	Stem	73	Spherical	95
34	Momordica cymbalaria	Fruit	15.5	Spherical	96
35	Helicteres isora	Root	30-40	Crystalline	97
36	Colotropis gigantea	Latex	5-30	Spherical	98
37	Tinospora cordifolia	Stem	60	Spherical	99

4. CHARACTERIZATION TECHNIQUES OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES

After preparation of silver nano particles it is necessary to do characterization. From characterization one can find out size, shape, morphology, structure, surface chemistry and surface area. The following characterization techniques are mostly used.

Table 2: characterization techniques of silver nanoparticles

ANALYSIS TYPE	CHARACTERIZATION TECHNIQUE	FUNCTION	Ref.
Spectroscopic techniques	Ultraviolet(UV)-visible spectroscopy	Used to determine the optical properties like absorbance, transmittance, confirms the formation of nano particles and detect their wavelength ranges.	100
	Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy(FT-IR)	Used to analyze the surface chemistry and to find out whether bio molecules are involved or not.	101
	Zeta potential	It provides information about particle stability by considering electronic charge	102
	Dynamic light scattering(DLS)	To study the average particle size of silver nanoparticles	103
X-ray based analysis	X-ray diffraction(XRD)	It is the main tool for finding characteristics like crystal structure, crystal phase size, and strain.	104
	X-ray photo electron spectroscopy(XPS)	Useful for determination of structure and composition of nanoparticles	105
	Energy dispersive spectroscopy(EDX)	Evaluate atomic structure, and provide elemental identification	106
Microscopic techniques	Scanning electron microscopy(SEM)	Useful for determination of particle shapes, surface morphology, size distribution of NPs.	107,108,81
	Transmission electron microscopy(TEM)	It measures size distribution, particle size and morphology of NPs.	109
	Atomic force microscopy(AFM)	Used to investigate the dispersion of NPs, size, shape and structure	2

5. APPLICATIONS OF NANOPARTICLES

Nanoparticles have gotten more attention in recent years because they are so small compared to their bulk materials. Because of this property, they could be used in many areas of technology, such as

catalysis, biotechnology, the chemical industry, electronics, and electro-optical devices [110,111]. Metal nanoparticles have a specific effect on cells, and their cytotoxicity depends on their size and shape [112,113]. Ag Nps are used for molecular labelling [113,114], and silver nanoparticles have been shown to be antiviral and antibacterial in many research studies [115].

Fig. 2: Applications of silver nano particles in different fields

5.1. Antibacterial activity:

The antimicrobial properties of silver nanoparticles are affected by factors such as size, pH, and ionic strength [116]. Silver nanoparticles can continuously release silver ions, which may be used to kill microbes [117]. Silver ions can adhere to the cell wall and cytoplasmic membrane due to electrostatic attraction and affinity for sulphur proteins. The adhered ion can increase cytoplasmic membrane permeability and disrupt the bacterial envelope [118].

5.2. Anticancer activity:

Cancer is an uncontrolled cell growth that frequently occurs in tumour cells and is accompanied by historical changes in biochemical and enzymatic parameters. By adopting bio-based Nps as new regulatory agents, the excessive increase of cellular growth in malignant cells will be stopped and regulated with cell cycle mechanism. [119]. Numerous studies have shown that Nps have the ability to regulate the proliferation of tumour cells. The secondary metabolites in the synthesising medium are responsible for the improved cytotoxic action. [120,121]

5.3. Antioxidant activity:

Antioxidant molecules, both enzyme- and non-enzyme-based, regulate the free radical process. Reactive oxygen species (ROS), such as H_2O_2 , produce the free radicals. Protein, glycoprotein, lipids, phenolics, flavanoids, and carbohydrates are examples of biomolecules that strongly regulate the free radical process. [122]. Antioxidants' ability to scavenge free radicals is helpful for managing a number of chronic diseases, including cancer, diabetes, and metabolic disorders. The silver Nps can exhibit more potent antioxidant qualities.

5.4. Antifungal activity:

High polymers of fatty acids and protein make up the fungal cell wall. The multifunctional Ag Nps actively suppress fungal growth and have favourable activity against fungi that produce spores. By applying metallic Nps to the fungus cell membrane, structural alterations were seen [123].

5.6. Catalytical activity:

Due to their high demand in the paper, leather, plastic, food, printing, textile, and pharmaceutical industries, organic dyes play a significant role in these sectors. These dye pollution is a major source of environmental contamination. Recent material research disciplines have taken a keen interest in the usage of metal and metal oxide nanoparticles like Ag Nps, which are useful for oxidising harmful pollutants [124-126]. Additionally, metal nanoparticles exhibit better photocatalytic destruction of several pollutant dyes. Metal Nps have been utilised most frequently for the detection of heavy metal ions in polluted water systems due to their adaptable size and various optical properties [127-128]. The reduction of 4-Nitro phenol to 4-Amino phenol also uses catalytic activity of the silver Nps.

5.6. Other Applications:

There have been several reports on the use of AgNPs in the field of medicine. The AgNPs have been used as therapeutic agents [129], as glyconano sensors for disease diagnosis [130] and as nano carriers for drugs delivery [131]. Reports are also available on the use of AgNPs in radiation therapy [132], in H₂O₂ sensor [133], in ESR-Dosimetry [134], as heavy metal ion sensors [135] and as catalyst for reduction of dyes such as methylene blue [136].

Table 3: List of studies performed using silver nanoparticles against various applications

<i>S.no</i>	<i>Plant used</i>	<i>Plant parts used</i>	<i>Size (nm)</i>	<i>Shape</i>	<i>Applications</i>	<i>Ref</i>
Antibacterial activity						
1	Capparis spinosa	Leaf	10-40	Spherical	B. cereus ,E. coli , S. aureus, S.typhimurium	[137]
2	Parkia speciosa Hassk	Stinky bean	20–50	Spherical (Aging) flake (microwave irradiation)	Escherichia coli, Staphylococcus aureus, Pseudomonas aeruginosa	[138]
3	Red apples	Fruit	30.25 ± 5.26	Spherical	E.coli,Staphylococcus aureus ,Pseudomonas aeruginosa	[139]
4	Protium serratum	Leaf	74.56 ± 0.46	Irregular spherical	Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Escherichia coli, Bacillus subtilis	[140]
5	Calliandra haematocep hala	Leaf	70	Spherical	Escherichia coli	[141]
6	Brassica rapa	Leaf	10-30	Spherical	Enterobactersp. Escherichia coli	[142]
7	Nelumbo nucifera	Leaf	30–40	Spherical	E.coli,Bacillus subtilis ,S-typhi ,Vibrio cholerae	[143]
8	Carica papaya Leaves	Leaf	50-40	Spherical	S. aureus, Bacillus subtilis , M. Luteus,P.putida ,K.Pneumoniae, Escherichia coli	[144]
9	Stachytarph era indica	Leaf	48.75	Spherical	Staphylococcus aureus, Bacillus subtilis, E.coli	[145]
10	Munronia pinnata	Leaf	57.29	Spherical	Bacillus subtilis ,E.coli , Staphylococcus aureus	[145]
11	Aloevera	Leaf	90	Spherical	Escherichia coli	[146]
12	Pongamia pinnata	Bark	30	Spherical	S.aureus, Bacillus subtilis	[147]
13	Capparis zeylanica	Leaf	23	Spherical	S. dysenteriae S. epidermis, E. faecalis, C.Albicans, A. niger, S. Paratyphi	[148]
14	Carya illinoensis	Leaf	12–30	Spherical	S.aureus ,L. monocytogenes ,E. coli, P. aeruginosa,	[149]
15	Cestrum nocturnum	Leaf	20	Spherical	E. faecalisS.typhi, E. coli, P. vulgaris and V. cholerae, Citrobacter,	[150]
16	Lantana trifolia	Leaf	5-70	Spherical	B. subtilis ,E. coli,P. aeruginosa, C.albicans,S. aureus	[151]
17	Mentha aquatica	Leaf	8	Spherical	E. coli, B.cereus, P. aeruginosa, and S. aureus	[152]
18	Caesalpinia pulcherrima	Leaf	9	Spherical	E. coli,P.aeruginosa, S. typhimurium,K. pneumoniae, C.albicans, C. glabrata,B. cereus, B. subtilis,S.aureus,C. rubrum	[153]

19	Scoparia dulcis	Leaf	12	Spherical	A. nigeralbicans ,P. aeruginosa, E. coli, B.subtilis,S.Aureus	[154]
20	Ligustrum lucidum	Leaf	13	Spherical	S. turcica	[155]
21	Curcuma longa L.	Leaf	25	Spherical	E. coli, C. albicans, S. aureus, P. aeruginosa, S. Pyogenes	[156]
22	Melaleuca alternifolia	Leaf	10-20	Spherical	K. pneumoniae, P.aeruginosa, T. mentagrophytes, C. albicans ,S. epidermidis, S.pyogenes S. aureus, methicillin-resistant	[157]
23	Aspilia pluriseta	Leaf	17	Spherical	P. aeruginosa, C. albicans ,B. subtilis,S. aureus,E. coli	[158]
24	Clerodendrum inerme	Leaf	6	Spherical	E. coli,,A. niger,T.harzianum, A. flavus ,B. subtilis,S. aureus	[159]
Anticancer activity						
25	Podophyllum hexandrum	Leaf	14	Spherical	Anticancer activity HeLa	[160]
26	Sesbania grandiflora	Leaf	22	Spherical	MCF-7	[161]
27	Suaeda monoica	Leaf	31	Spherical	Hep-2	[162]
28	Gelsemium sempervirens	Whole plant	112	Spherical	Cytotoxicity	[163]
29	H. canadensis	Whole plant	113	Spherical	Anti-cancer	[164]
30	Melia azedarach	Leaves	78	Irregular	Anti-cancer	[165]
31	Vitex negundo L	Leaf	22	Spherical	HCT-15	[166]
32	Cymodocea serrulata	Whole plant	17-29	Spherical	HeLa	[167]
33	Gymnema sylvestre	Leaf	----	Spherical	HT29	[168]
34	Moringa oleifera	leaf	94	spherical,cuboidal	A431	[169]
35	Plumeria Alba	flower	36	Spherical	COLO 205	[170]
36	Azadirachta indica	leaf	2–18	Triangular, hexagonal	SiHa	[171]
37	A. indica	Leaf		Spherical	HeLa, MCF-7	[172]
Antifungal activity						

38	<i>Musa paradisiaca</i>	peel	20	Nano-clusters	Antifungal and antibacterial	[173]
39	Green and black tea	leaf	10-20	Spherical	Anti fungal <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>A. parasiticus</i>	[174]
40	<i>Dodonaea viscosa</i> and <i>Hyptis suaveolens</i>	leaf	40-55	Spherical	<i>Candida albicans</i> , <i>C. glabrata</i> , <i>C. tropicalis</i> , clinical isolate	[175]
41	<i>Bergenia ciliata</i>	Whole plant	35	Spherical	<i>F. solani</i> , <i>A. niger</i> , <i>A. flavus</i> , <i>A. Fumigatus</i>	[176]
42	<i>Trifolium resupinatum</i>	seed extract	5-10	Spherical	<i>N. parvum</i> , <i>R. solani</i>	[177]
43	<i>Rosa indica</i> .		23–60	Spherical	Antimicrobial, carcinogenic and anti-inflammatory	[178]
Antioxidant activity						
44	<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i>	Whole plant	40	Spherical	Antioxidant, antimicrobial	[179]
45	<i>Citrullus colocynthis</i>	Calli	36	Triangle	Antioxidant, anticancer	[180]
46	<i>Alpinia</i>	seed	12.6	Spherical	Antioxidant, anticancer, Antibacterial	[181]
47	<i>Clerodendrum Phlomidis</i>	leaf	23-42	Spherical	Antioxidant, anticancer	[182]
48	<i>Ficus carica</i>	Fruit	10-30	Spherical	Antioxidant	[183]
49	<i>Momordica charantia</i>	fruit	10-16	Spherical	Degradation of dyes	[184]
50	<i>Jasminum Subtripinarve</i>	leaves	5-35	Spherical	Degradation of pollutants, 4-NP	[185]
51	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	flower	8.5	Spherical	Degradation of dyes, 4-NP	[186]
52	<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	Unripe fruit	20-30	Spherical	Photo degradation of dye	[187]
53	<i>Anacardium Occidentale</i>	testa	25	Spherical	Degradation of Azo-dyes	[188]
54	<i>Zanthoxylum Armatum</i>	leaves	15-50	Spherical	Degradation of dyes	[189]

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVE

The synthesis process is an important step in the formation of nanoparticles. And it determines the size and shape of formed silver NPs. The major advantage of green process is less cost, low energy consumption and large scale-up capability. Plant extracts that contain natural compounds such as alkaloids, flavonoids, and polyhydroxy compounds can produce reducing and capping ability. Several factors such as temperature of reaction, reagent concentration and solution pH are responsible for different sizes of silver nanoparticles. Silver nanoparticles play an important role in health care because they are used as antibacterial and antitumor agents, and other uses are in food packaging, agriculture field. Everyone knows that the majority of antibiotics that are used without a plan cause bacteria to become

resistant, which makes the antibiotics useless. Because of this, bacteria that make biofilms are a major cause for concern. As a way to deal with the problem of antibiotic resistance, more and more attention is being paid to non-antibiotic treatments all over the world. Other strategies could include coating or embedding the surface with nanomaterials or using silver nanoparticles as anti-biofilm agents. Also, silver nanoparticles have been studied the most and used in the treatment of number of diseases like cancer, wound healing, dental implants, and other therapies that involve changing the way biological processes. Once we learn more about them and improve our technology to the point where we can use them effectively, these special particles will be used in medicine as a standard way to prevent and treat diseases that are resistant to multiple drugs.

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